

1 **Growth factor induction during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC.**

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7 Hepatocyte growth factor, *HGF* and the nerve growth factor *VGF* were both highly activated. *FGF2* and
8 *FGF13* were activated, as were *FGF* receptors including *FGFRL1*, *FGFR3* and *FGFR4*. *VEGF* was
9 present in large quantities. *IGFBP5* and *IGFBP7* were repressed but the significance of this was not clear.

10 Citations

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